

ISic0915

I.Sicily inscription 0915

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of San Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. ἐνθάδε κῆτε Δι
2. ονυσία τελευτή
3. σα[σα] τῆ πρὸ ζ κα(λανδῶν) Σεπτε
4. βρήον ἐνθάδε
5. κῆτε ὁ Κτησίβις

Apparatus

Text of IG

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492545

EDCS 39102072

PHI 140396

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0098 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 60.1018

Curbera, J.B. 2010. four intriguing names. In Catling, R. W. V., Marchand, F. (eds.), *Onomatologos. Studies in Greek Personal Names presented to Elaine Matthews.* Oxford. pp. 601-605. At 604-605

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0915. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4340050>